

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF ASYMMETRIC CASCADED H-BRIDGE INVERTERS

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ABSTRACT

Inverters are the devices which are used to convert DC supply into AC supply. Inverters are used in power system applications, speed control of induction motors and synchronous motor, uninterrupted power supplies and industries etc. Inverters also named as power inverter that converts direct current to alternating current at any required voltage and frequency. Normal inverter produces three levels, these are limited by the output voltage issues such as harmonic distortion and voltage stress, which can be mitigated by multilevel inverter. A hybrid inverter is a power electronic converter that combines with different topologies to achieve a higher number of output voltages level with less distortion and harmonic content.

KEYWORDS

Asymmetric, Cascaded, Multi Level Inverter, H-bridge

1. INTRODUCTION

A multi-level inverter is a power conversion device that generates a stepped AC output waveform by synthesizing multiple voltage levels. These inverters reduce the harmonic content in the output signal and improve the efficiency of the system, as compared to conventional two-level inverters. The cascaded multi-level inverter uses a series of H-bridge cells connected in a cascaded arrangement. Each H-bridge can be controlled independently, allowing the inverter to produce several distinct voltage levels. By adding more H-bridge cells, the inverter can produce an output with a higher number of voltage levels, which reduces the harmonic distortion.

The hybrid aspect of the cascaded multi-level inverter refers to combining different inverter topologies, like cascaded H-bridge inverter and diode-clamped or flying capacitor inverters. This hybridization aims in enhancing the overall performance.

A hybrid control strategy combining Nearest Level Control (NLC) and Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) for a 9-level Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter (CHB-MLI). The goal is to improve output voltage control and reduce Total Harmonic Distortion (THD). This hybrid method performs individual NLC or PWM in both voltage control range and THD. The authors also suggested further improvements using filters, Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE), and metaheuristic algorithms[1].

An asymmetric Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter (CHB-MLI) that uses only one DC source per phase, with the remaining bridges powered by floating capacitor has been introduced. These capacitors self-balance without closed-loop control, eliminating the traditional need for multiple isolated DC sources. A rule-based switching strategy is proposed to manage switching redundancies and ensure voltage balance[2].

An efficient multicarrier Sinusoidal Pulse Width Modulation (SPWM) technique for a symmetrical Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter (CHB-MLI) has been presented. The number of output voltage levels depends on the number of DC sources used — two sources yield five levels, and three sources yield seven. The SPWM strategy involves a sine wave as the reference and a triangular wave as the carrier, improving output voltage waveform quality and reducing Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)[3].

A novel homotopy algorithm designed for determining the optimal switching angles in Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE) for Cascaded H-Bridge (CHB) Multilevel Inverters has been introduced. This algorithm addresses the complex nonlinear transcendental equations involved in SHE. It is both efficient and reliable, offering rapid convergence and simplified mathematical derivation, and the approach is scalable to higher-level inverters.

An online precise model to calculate conduction and switching losses based on actual current waveforms and device characteristics. Selective Harmonic Elimination (SHE) was used for control, with Genetic Algorithm (GA) implemented to determine optimal switching angles. The simulation results revealed that while conduction losses increase with more inverter levels, switching losses decrease, and THD significantly reduces as the number of levels increases[5].

2. METHODOLOGY

The cascaded H-Bridge inverter consists of multiple H-bridge units connected in series. Each H-bridge is capable of producing three possible voltage levels: $+V_{dc}$, 0, and $-V_{dc}$, where V_{dc} is the DC supply voltage to each individual bridge. By connecting several bridge cells in series, a multilevel output voltage can be achieved.

It consists of Individual Bridge Cells. Each bridge has four switches (usually IGBTs or MOSFETs and antiparallel diodes connected across them), a DC voltage source, and a load. The bridge can be operated to generate three distinct output voltage levels. The output voltage of the system is the sum of the voltages from all individual bridges, which allows for the creation of a higher number of voltage levels and a smoother output waveform.

The voltage waveform produced by a cascaded H-Bridge inverter is nearly sinusoidal, and the harmonic content is significantly reduced which makes the system more efficient and less prone to electrical noise and equipment damage.

3. MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

An Integrated Mathematical modeling of Hybrid cascaded Multi level inverter is developed in this chapter. In this method output is produced using pulse generator circuits which creates timing signals for various switches in the circuit.

The switching states for the Inverter's power electronic devices (IGBTs, MOSFETs) are presented in this chapter.

Circuit Diagram

Figure1 Hybrid Cascaded Multilevel Inverter

Figure 1 represents the asymmetrical Hybrid Cascaded Multilevel configuration with two inverters connected in series, inverters are supplied with different input voltages. A modern multilevel inverter named as Hybrid Cascaded multilevel (HCHB) with asymmetrical configuration is implemented. This type of inverter is highly used in PV based grid system. Fig3.2.1 indicates the 9-level hybrid cascaded multilevel inverter. It is the series combination of two inverters. The first Bridge inverter gets power supply from Vdc source. The second Bridge inverter gets power supply from dc supply which is 3 times that of first inverter's supply(3Vdc). The first bridge inverter gives Vdc as output when switch S1, S4 are ON, have output -Vdc when switch S2, S3 are ON and output 0 when all the switches are off. Similarly, the second bridge inverter can give ±3Vdc and 0V. When switch S1*, S4* are ON the output is 3Vdc, when switch S2*, S3* are ON the output is -3Vdc and the output is 0 when all switches are OFF. To generate 9-level output voltage waveform we need 0V, ±1V, ±2V, ±3V, ± 4V, and this can be generating as per the following switching scheme which is given in Table-I.

Desired output	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1*	S2*	S3*	S4*
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vdc	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
2Vdc	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1
3Vdc	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
4Vdc	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1
-Vdc	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
-2Vdc	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0
-3Vdc	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
-4Vdc	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0

Table I-Representation of switches to be ON or OFF

Switching functions represent the switching stages of the inverter's power electronic devices (IGBT). Each level in the inverter is controlled by switching the devices ON or OFF, and the state of each switch determines the output voltage. The total output voltage is constructed as a sum of individual contributions for each level, considering specific switching sequence for each. This can be expressed as

$$V_{out}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^n V_k \cdot sk(t)$$

Where, V_k is the voltage contribution from the inverters, $sk(t)$ is the switching function representing whether the switch is ON(1) or OFF(0) at a given time.

$sk(t)=1$, if the pair of switches are ON and provide positive output

$sk(t)=-1$, if the pair of switches are ON and provide negative output

In order to get the output voltage as Vdc output voltage switches S1 and S4 should be ON,

$$\begin{aligned} V_{out}(t) &= V_{dc} * 1 + v_{dc} * 0 + 3V_{dc} * 0 + 3V_{dc} * 0 \\ &= V_{dc} \end{aligned}$$

In order to get the output voltage as -2Vdc switches S1, S4 and S2*,S3* should be ON

$$\begin{aligned} V_{out}(t) &= V_{dc} * 1 + V_{dc} * 0 + 3V_{dc} * (-1) + 3V_{dc} * 0 \\ &= -2V_{dc} \end{aligned}$$

As per the above analysis the switches are provided with pulses at different intervals in order to get different output voltage levels.

The output voltage of an asymmetrical Hybrid Cascaded Multi level inverter is the sum of the voltage contribution from each individual stage where each stage can have a different set of voltage levels. This allows the inverter to reduce harmonic distortion and improving the overall performance of the inverter system. The switching states of the individual stages determine the instantaneous output voltage at any given time.

4. IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

The realization of the proposed method involves combining various types of power electronic components, with advanced modulation techniques to achieve the desired performance. The method focuses on optimizing the inverter design to minimize switching losses while maintaining the ability to handle high voltage and current ratings.

The hybrid structure of the cascaded multilevel inverter enables it to generate a higher number of output voltage levels by employing a combination of series and parallel connected power cells. This not only enhances the overall performance of the inverter but also ensures better utilization of the available DC sources, which can be from renewable energy sources like solar or wind power. Testing the hybrid cascaded multilevel inverter (HCMI) under different operational conditions is essential to validate the performance improvements claimed by the proposed method. The test system is designed to simulate real-world applications, and the conclusions drawn from the test results can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the inverter's design and control strategies.

HYBRID CASCADED MULTILEVEL INVERTER

In this topology, a series of single-phase inverter are linked and connected together. For 9 level Cascaded H- Bridge multilevel inverter with asymmetric configuration circuit consists of H-Bridge with two Direct Current (DC) supply of different magnitude. As we know each H-Bridge can give $\pm V_{dc}$ and 0. For 9- level Cascaded H-Bridge multilevel inverter we need $\pm V_{dc}$, $\pm 2V_{dc}$, $\pm 3V_{dc}$, $\pm 4V_{dc}$ and 0. This voltage level can be achieved by operating the two bridges in a specific manner.

Figure2. Simulink model of 9 level Hybrid cascaded multilevel inverter

Switching Scheme of 9 level HCMLI

First Inverter	Second Inverter	Active Switches	Desired Output
0	0	-	0
Vdc	0	S1, S4	Vdc
-Vdc	3Vdc	S2, S3, S1*, S4*	2Vdc
0	3Vdc	S1*, S4*	3Vdc
Vdc	3Vdc	S1, S4, S1*, S4*	4Vdc
-Vdc	0	S2, S3	-Vdc
Vdc	-3Vdc	S1, S4, S2*, S3*	-2Vdc
0	-3Vdc	S2*, S3*	-3Vdc
-Vdc	-3Vdc	S2, S3, S2*, S3*	-4Vdc

Table II-Switching Scheme

5.RESULTS

Based on the above switching scheme ,the switching pulses are given to the respective switches present in the two bridges and the desired output is produced.

Figure 3: Switching pulses for s1,s4

Figure 4: Switching pulses for s2, s3

6. CONCLUSION

The 9-level hybrid cascaded multilevel inverter produces smooth output with moderate harmonic distortion and lower switching losses. Similarly the 19-level inverter delivers a much smoother, near-sinusoidal output with lower Total Harmonic Distortion (THD), ideal for high-performance or sensitive loads, though it comes with increased complexity and cost. By employing hybrid cascaded Multi level inverter topology the number of power switches required are minimized therefore switching and conduction losses get reduced improving the quality of the output waveform.

7. REFERENCES

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